

SEASONAL VARIATIONS IN THE LEACHATE CHARACTERISTICS IN MSW SITES

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ABSTRACT

Characterization of leachate from Municipal Solid Waste (MSW) dumpsites of Vijayawada city in Andhra Pradesh (India) was done during wet and dry seasons. Leachate samples were collected and analyzed for various physico-chemical parameters and heavy metals to estimate its pollution potential. The study helps to design a more efficient and effective MSW management technique suitable for the city for reducing the harmful impacts posed from the MSW dumpsites. The two MSW dump sites of Vijayawada city are non-engineered open dumps. They have neither any bottom liner nor any leachate collection and treatment system. Therefore, all the leachate generated finds its paths into the surrounding environment. Seasonal changes in the physico-chemical properties of leachate were also discussed in the paper. The results prompt an urgent need for adapting the leachate collection and treatment procedures and enhancing the stabilization of the leachate in the MSW dumps through biodegradation. A continuous monitoring of the leachate and ground water quality is recommended at the dumpsites.

KEYWORDS: Municipal Solid Waste (MSW), Leachate, dumpsites, ground water, heavy metals.

INTRODUCTION:

The overall effects of urbanization, population growth and widespread industrialization have lead to extreme environmental damages. One of most neglected areas is waste management in most of the low and middle income countries like India. The primary reasons are attributed to inadequate technical and financial resources on top of the absence of political will, unwillingness of stakeholders, and lack of local awareness (Mcdougall, 2001, NWQS REPORT, 2005, AIT, 1994). MSW management gets the lowest priority, mainly because disruptions and deficiencies in it do not directly and immediately affect public life and cause public reaction. The per capita generation of MSW has also increased tremendously with improved life style and social status of the populations in urban centers (Sharholy, 2007). Today more than 45 million tonnes/year of solid waste is generated from the urban centres of

India which are collected inefficiently, transported inadequately and disposed unscientifically (TERE, 1998) As more land is needed for the ultimate disposal of these solid wastes, issues related to disposal have become highly challenging. (Idris et al, 2004). Seeing the scenario of increase in generation, improper utilization and disposal of waste in the country, the Ministry of Environment and Forest (MoEF) has Municipal Solid Waste (Management and Handling) Rules, 2000, which states that Municipal Solid Waste (MSW) is commercial and residential wastes generated in a municipal or notified areas in either solid or semi-solid form, excluding industrial hazardous wastes but including treated biomedical wastes. These solid wastes are generally disposed off in a low lying area called sanitary landfill area by the municipal authorities. In practice, the usage of landfills as waste disposal sites in developing countries is generally far from standard recommendations (Oyeku, 2010). Land filling involves appropriate control of leachate and landfill gas with the existence of lined pit (Alloway, 1997). It may not be technologically advance but continuous maintenance and monitoring is essential to ensure safe operation (Uriarte, 2008). Since the solid waste dumps are heterogeneous in nature, and the degradation time results in longer retention of the waste thereby increasing the chances of movement of leachate down the ground water source and contaminating the water (Iqbal et al, 2009)

Considering these concerns, possible impact to surrounding environment brought by landfills is inevitable. It may bring ecological and health associated risks if poorly managed like contaminating the groundwater (Oyeku, 2010; Mor 2006; Agrawal, 2011 & Longe, 2010). The composition of leachate depends upon the nature of solid waste buried, chemical and biochemical processes responsible for the decomposition of waste materials, and water content in total waste (Fatta et al., 1999 & Mor et al., 2006). The landfill leachate contains a high concentration of organic matters and inorganic ions, including heavy metals (Baun et al., 2000). Thus it is well known from the literature that the landfill leachate may cause a serious environmental problem caused to discharge heavy metals continuously, if it is not under control (Poon and Chen, 1999; Abu-Rukah and Al-Kofahi, 2001; Nanny and Ratasuk, 2002; Huan-Jung et al., 2006 & Mor et al., 2006). Common metals found in leachate include the following with their average amounts: copper (Cu) (5 ppm), zinc (Zn) (50 ppm), lead (Pb) (0.30 ppm), and mercury (Hg) (60 ppb) [12]. Olivero-Verbel et al., (2007) found that the landfill leachates contained high concentrations of Cd, Hg, Ni, Mn, Cu and Pb where the toxicity of leachates depends on the concentration of such metals (especially Cd) associated with organic matter.

STUDY AREA

Vijayawada is the second largest city in the state of divided Andhra Pradesh, India, after Visakhapatnam, with an area of 261.88 km² and population of 1,048,240. Vijayawada is surrounded by the Krishna River on the east and west and the Budameru River on the north. The northern, northwestern, and southwestern parts of the city are covered by a low range of hills, while the central, southwestern and northwestern parts are covered by rich and fertile agriculture lands with three major irrigation canals. The topography of Vijayawada is flat, with a few small- to medium-sized hills. The Krishna River runs through the city. These hills are part of the Eastern Ghats cut through by the Krishna River. The city generates solid waste of 650 Tons/Day. Generally low lying areas and outskirts of the city Vijayawada are used for the purpose of open dumping. In addition uncontrolled release of landfill gas, burning of open dumps can cause air pollution. The main risks of human health arise from the breeding of disease vectors, primary flies and rats thriving in the exposed garbage and refuse dumps (Niloufer et al., 2013). The two MSW dump sites at Pathapadu suburban region of Vijayawada and Ajith Singnagar are been selected for the present study.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Leachate Sampling:

Leachate sample was collected from two MSW dumpsites of Vijayawada i.e. Pathapadu dumpsite (PPD) in the suburban region of Vijayawada and Ajith Singhnagar dumpsite (ASN). Site descriptions are given below in the table 1. The two dumpsites i.e. Pathapadu dumpsite (PPD) and Ajith Singhnagar dumpsite (ASN) are studied on a monthly basis to analyse the leachate quality for specific parameters like temperature, pH, Total dissolved solids (TDS), Electrical conductivity (EC), Biological oxygen demand (BOD), Chemical oxygen demand (COD), fluorides, chlorides and heavy metals like Boron (B), Cadmium (Cd), Chromium (Cr), Nickel (Ni), Zinc (Zn), Copper (Cu) and Lead (Pb) to determine pollution potential of leachate discharge from MSW landfill site to estimate its pollution potential. The two sites were non-engineered open dumps. The ASN dumpsite had neither any bottom liner nor any leachate collection and treatment system. Therefore, all the leachate generated finds its paths into the surrounding environment. The landfill site is not equipped with any leachate collectors.

Leachate Analysis:

The leachate quality parameters were analysed as per the methods described in “Standard methods for examination of water and wastewater” by American Public Health Association [47]. The Temperature was measured by a Digital Thermometer with measuring range -50°C- + 300°C. The pH was measured by pocket sized pH tester (HANNA make) whereas, Conductivity/TDS was measured by DiST Conductivity/TDS Meters with Automatic Temperature Compensation (HANNA make). Fluorides were estimated by SPADNS method using Spectrophotometer. Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) was determined by refluxion of sample followed by titration with Ferrous Ammonium Sulphate (FAS). Biological Oxygen Demand (BOD) - Winkler’s method was used for estimating initial and final DO in the sample and BOD was determined. Argentometric volumetric titration method in the presence of Potassium chromate provides reliable results of chloride. Heavy metals such as Pb, Cu, Cr, and Cd in both leachate and groundwater samples are determined in total form. Nitric acid (HNO₃) digestion is employed prior to Flame-AAS analysis pre-calibrated with standards.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Leachate samples were collected at the two dumpsites viz PPD and ASN dumpsites (Pathapadu and Ajith singhnagar dumpsites). The sampling was done for complete two seasons of the annual cycle i.e. wet season (June 2013 to December 2013) and dry season (January 2014 to May 2014).

Table 1: Dumpsite Description

Disposal Characteristics	Pathapadu (PPD)	Ajith Singnagar (ASN)
In operation (Years)	5	7
Total area (Acres)	2	106.6
Disposal quantity(MT/day)	360	225
Waste Disposal method	Land filling	Open dumping
Liner	Lined	Unlined
Condition	Closed	Active
Current land use	Unused	Unused
Type of area	Semi-urban	Urban

Table 2: Characteristics of Leachate in Wet and Dry Seasons

Parameter	Wet Season		Dry Season		STANDARDS (Mode of Disposal)**		
	PPD (Mean ± SD)	ASN (Mean ± SD)	PPD (Mean ± SD)	ASN (Mean ± SD)	Inland Surface Water	Public Sewers	Land disposal
Temperature (°C)	27.31 ± 0.80	27.87 ± 0.28	30.68 ± 0.80	30.88 ± 0.41	--	--	--
pH	7.75 ± 0.26	7.55 ± 0.20	8.28 ± 0.08	8.32 ± 0.16	5.5 to 9.0	5.5 to 9.0	5.5 to 9.0
TDS	8106 ± 751.13	8426 ± 815.54	9228.2±1134.23	7637.6±588.20	2100	2100	2100
EC(μhos/cm)	12098.93± 1323.70	12576.76 ± 1217.22	14939.8±558.43	1923.88±689.90	--	--	--
BOD	589.85 ± 75.27	482.85 ± 19.13	671.6 ± 103.8	428.94±241.49	30	350	100
COD	798 ± 154.11	871 ± 46.97	4082 ± 99.12	3818±65.82	250	--	--
Fluorides	0.58 ± 0.28	1.13 ± 0.39	1.61 ± 0.79	2.43 ± 0.41	2.0	1.5	--
Chlorides	1903.14 ± 139.42	1450.85 ±156.13	13925±318.81	10944±113.89	1000	1000	600
Boron	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	--	--	--
Cadmium	0.098 ± 0.063	0.072 ± 0.015	0.19 ± 0.006	0.16 ± 0.03	2.0	1.0	--
Chromium	ND	ND	ND	ND	2.0	2.0	--
Nickel	0.379 ± 0.37	0.721 ± 0.26	1.10 ± 0.12	1.64 ± 0.48	3.0	3.0	--
Zinc	0.334 ± 0.025	1.60 ± 0.60	0.29 ± 0.03	2.68 ± 0.28	5.0	15	--
Copper	0.48 ± 0.08	0.63 ± 0.17	1.48 ± 0.52	1.22 ± 0.72	3.0	3.0	--
Lead	0.098 ± 0.03	0.202 ± 0.08	0.14 ± 0.02	0.16 ± 0.04	0.1	1.0	--

* All vaules in mg/L except for pH and EC

** Municipal Solid Waste (Management and Handling) Rules, 2000

Temperature (°C): The temperature ranged between 26.8 to 32.1 at PPD dumpsite with mean value of 27.31 and 27.4 to 31.4 at ASN dumpsite with mean value of 27.87. The temperature during the study period remained uniform throughout the year and very minor differences can be observed.

pH: Higher pH values of 7.6 to 8.3 were recorded from the stabilized leachate of PPD dumpsite and 7.2 to 8.5 at ASN dumpsite (Table 2) representing that both the dumpsites are in methanogenic phase. There is a general consensus that the lower pH cluster represents the acid producing phase and the upper cluster represents the methanogenic phase. During the initial stage the pH values are low, while during the methanogenic stage the pH appeared to be neutral to alkaline. (Musa, 2014). Initial low pH is due to high concentration of volatile fatty acids (Bohdziewicz et al., 2008). Stabilized leachate shows fairly constant pH with little

variations and it may range between 7.5 and 9. Chian and DeWalle, (1976) reported that the pH of leachate increased with time due to the decrease of the concentration of the partially ionized free volatile fatty acids (Chian et al., 1976). The increase in pH suggested that a steady state has been reached between acid producing processes (e.g., cellulose and lignin degradation) and acid consuming processes (e.g., methane formation) at the landfill (Chu et al., 1994). (Bhalla, 2012). Feebly alkaline nature of leachate is an indicator of the mature stage of the dumping site (Jorstad et al., 2004)

TDS: The TDS ranged between 7180 to 10,241 mg/L at PPD dumpsite and 7234 to 9878 mg/L at ASN dumpsite. The average of the annual cycle was 8106 mg/L and 8426 mg/L in wet season, whereas 9228.2 and 7637.6 mg/L in dry season at both the dumpsites which exceeded the standards given by MSW(M & H) Rules, 2000. Archana and Dutta, (2014) and Bhalla et al., (2013) also have reported high values of TDS in wet season than in dry season. The concentrations of TDS in all sites in both seasons have exceeded the standards permitted by MSW (management and handling) Rules, 2000 (Table 2).

EC: EC is a valuable indicator of the amount of material dissolved in water whereas Sophocleous et al., (2002) stated that, the high values of EC can be attributed to the high levels of the various anions. The EC has ranged between 10,716.41 to 15238.8 $\mu\text{hos/cm}$ at PPD dumpsite and 10797.01 to 13247.76 $\mu\text{hos/cm}$ at ASN dumpsite. The average EC in the two dumpsites was 12098.93 and 12576.76 $\mu\text{hos/cm}$ in wet season, 14939.8 and 1923.88 $\mu\text{hos/cm}$ in dry seasons respectively which were higher than the permissible limits (Table 2).

BOD: The presence of water pollutants limits the DO as a result of organic discharges. BOD is the measure of biodegradable organic mass of leachate and that indicates the maturity of the landfill which typically decreases with time (Qasim et al., 1994). In this study, the average BOD values for leachate at both the dumpsites were 589.85 mg/l, 482.85 mg/l in wet season whereas 671.6 and 428.94 mg/L in dry season respectively. Similar results were reported by Pratibha Dsouza and Somashekar, (2013). The measured BOD values were considerably higher than the standard limit. BOD value varies according to age of landfills. BOD value varies from 100-200 mg/l (Tchobanoglous, 1993).

COD: COD represents the amount of oxygen required to completely oxidize the organic waste constituents chemically to inorganic end products. The COD at the two dumpsites was 798 mg/l and 871 mg/l in wet season and 4082 and 3818 mg/L in dry season, respectively. The measured COD values were considerably higher than the specified limit.

Fluorides: The average values were 0.58 mg/L and 1.13 mg/L in wet season, whereas 1.61 and 2.43 mg/L in dry season at both the dumpsites which were within the standards but exceeded the standards given by MSW(M & H) Rules, 2000 at the ASN dumpsite in dry season. As the ASN dumpsite is located in a residential zone, the ground water contamination is a major issue in this region.

Chlorides: The average values were 1903.14 mg/L and 1450.85 mg/L in wet season, whereas 13925 and 10944mg/L in dry season at PPD and ASN dumpsites respectively. The chloride concentrations exceeded the standards and the concentrations were more in wet season than the dry season. According to Deng and Englehardt, (2007), the concentration of chlorides may range between 200-300 mg/l for a 1-2 year old landfill and the concentration decreases to 100-400 for a landfill greater than 5-10 years old [Deng 2006 73]. According to the study of Pratibha Dsouza and Somashekar, (2013) the concentration of chlorides was high in wet season than in the dry season.

Heavy Metals: Among the heavy metals analysed (i.e. B, Cd, Cr, Cu, Pb, Ni & Zn) concentrations in leachate were in trace amount as the waste is domestic in nature at both the PPD and ASN dumpsites which were within the standards given by MSW (M & H) Rules, 2000. Boron was below detection levels and chromium was not detected at both the dumpsites. The concentrations of heavy metals were found to be high in dry season and low in wet season in both the dumpsites. Concentration of heavy metals in a landfill is generally higher at earlier stages because of higher metal solubility as a result of low pH caused by production of organic acids (Kulikowska, 2008). As a result of decreased pH at later stages, a decrease in metal solubility occurs resulting in rapid decrease in concentration of heavy metals except lead because lead is known to produce very heavy complex with humic acids (Harmsen, 1983).

Conclusion:

Leachate produced during wet season was more alkaline as compared to those produced during dry period. Leachate collected during wet period showed lower concentrations of pollutants particularly for Total dissolved solids, EC, BOD, COD, boron, cadmium, chromium, copper, lead, nickel and zinc and were high in dry season (Tables 2.0 and 3.0). This could be attributed to the dilution effect of rainfall in the wet season that may have increased the concentrations of pollutants in the leachate. Hence landfills must be designed with a liner system at the base with proper drainage of leachate from the base of a landfill to the sides of the landfill and removal of the leachate from within the landfill. The landfills which receive runoff from outside they must also be provided with final cover to avoid percolation of water from the surface.

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